

IMPETUS

Turning climate commitments into action

Methodological note: Analysis of coastal erosion and shoreline dynamics using remote sensing

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1 Introduction and background

This methodological note outlines the procedures used to analyze Catalonia's coastal erosion and shoreline dynamics through satellite imagery. The study utilized optical images from Landsat and Sentinel-2 satellites to evaluate coastal morphological changes. These two sources were used for a regional analysis of the whole coast of Catalonia (Landsat) and three local beaches of the region: Pals, Santa Susanna, and Altafulla. The approach integrates data preprocessing, classification, validation, and temporal analysis to ensure reliable and actionable results.

2 Study area

The analysis focused on the coastal region of Catalonia, located in northeastern Spain, which spans approximately 580 km of Mediterranean coastline. Additionally, three specific beaches were chosen to represent diverse erosion scenarios:

- Pals Beach: Located on the Costa Brava, characterized by extensive dunes and a protected natural environment.
- Santa Susanna Beach: An urbanized beach in the Maresme region, exemplifying the interaction between infrastructure and natural dynamics.
- Altafulla Beach: A sandy beach on the Costa Dorada showcasing a stable coastal configuration.

Figure 1 Figure demonstrating the area of interest and the location of the three local sites analysed in this document.

3 Data Sources

The study utilized data from two satellite missions: Landsat and Sentinel-2, both processed using Google Earth Engine (GEE) [1].

- **Landsat Missions (Landsat 5, 7, and 8)** [2]: Annual mean composites were generated using all available cloud-free images from 1984 to 2023 at a 30-meter resolution, allowing for long-term shoreline evolution analysis. This source was used on the Catalonia's assessment producing annual means used to carry out shoreline delineation, providing insights from inter-annual shoreline evolution.
- **Sentinel-2 Missions (Sentinel-2A and 2B, L1C - Top of Atmosphere)** [3]: Higher-resolution imagery (10 meters) was available from 2015 to 2023. In this case, individual images were used to extract waterlines, enabling the study of intra-annual shoreline variability. This source was only used in the three local sites: Pals, Santa Susanna and Altafulla. Waterlines were produced to be able to study the intra-annual evolution and trend of the water-land delineation.

Both datasets underwent the same classification, shoreline delineation, and validation processes, ensuring that trends and variability observed were robust across different spatial and temporal resolutions.

4 Methodology

4.1 Data preprocessing

- Annual mean pixel-wise from all Landsat imagery available.

4.2 Classification of Land and Water

Three different classification methods for Land and water were used on the downloaded data and later their accuracy was compared.

- **Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI):**
 - Formula: $NDWI = (Green - NIR) / (Green + NIR)$
 - Bands used:
 - Green Band: Band 3 (Sentinel-2), Band 2 (Landsat)
 - Near Infrared (NIR) Band: Band 8 (Sentinel-2), Band 4 (Landsat)
 - Threshold: Pixels with $NDWI > 0$ were classified as water, and those with $NDWI \leq 0$ were classified as land.
- **K-means Algorithm.** Input Bands: Blue, Green, and NIR
 - Classification: Two clusters for land and water were created without prior training data.
 - Clustering was optimized using the Euclidean distance to minimize intra-cluster variance.
- **Slope Index (SI):**
 - Formula: $SI = (Red - Blue) \times Scale\ Factor$
 - Bands used:
 - Red Band: Band 4 (Sentinel-2), Band 3 (Landsat)
 - Blue Band: Band 2 (Sentinel-2), Band 1 (Landsat)
 - Scale Factor: 0.0001 to convert digital numbers to reflectance.
 - Positive SI values indicated specific terrain features, aiding in shoreline delineation

4.3 Shoreline/Waterline Delineation and Vectorization

To accurately map the shoreline and waterline along the Catalan coast and the three study beaches, the following steps were carried out:

Instantaneous waterlines:

- For Sentinel-2 imagery, individual images were processed to extract instantaneous waterlines, representing the boundary between land and water at a specific point in time.
- Water-land classified areas were converted from raster to polygonal vectors.
- The largest polygon, representing the water body, was extracted and converted into a line to delineate the waterline.

Mean annual delineation:

For Landsat imagery, the annual mean of all cloud-free images was used to generate a long-term shoreline, which represents the average position of all detected waterlines over a given year.

Smoothing Process:

To enhance the natural representation of the coastline, both waterline and shoreline vectors were smoothed using the Taubin smoothing method (Taubin, 1995 [4]).

4.4 Temporal and Statistical Analysis

- Temporal changes in the shoreline/waterline were analyzed across all available imagery of each satellite to identify variability and trends.
- A series of transects, spaced at 10-meter (Sentinel) and 30-meter (Landsat) intervals and perpendicular to the shoreline, were established for error calculation in the following step.

4.5 Shoreline/Waterline Delineation and Vectorization

- High-resolution orthophotos from the Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya were used as ground truth data. The shorelines were manually digitized for these orthophotos.
- Shorelines from Sentinel-2 imagery were compared to these manually digitized shorelines from orthophotos to ensure classification accuracy.
- Statistical metrics for error were calculated:
 - Root Mean Square Error (RMSE): Evaluated the deviation between derived and reference shorelines.
 - Bias: Measured systematic overestimation or underestimation of shoreline positions

5 Results

- **Accuracy:**

NDWI outperformed K-means and SI in most cases, with RMSE values ranging from 11.2 to 21.37 meters, indicating sub-pixel accuracy. Results are shown in the table below

Table 1 - Results of the comparison of the different methods with respect to the available orthophotos.

	RMSE (m)		BIAS (m)	
	K-Means	NDWI	K-Means	NDWI
2017-01	15.85	21.37	12.56	16.56
2019-10	18.61	16.42	16.76	9.65
2019-12	16.75	11.12	14.24	8.88
2020-01	23.35	19.91	20.01	13.02

- **Shoreline Variability:**

- Pals Beach: Pals Beach exhibits significant fluctuations, as indicated by high standard deviation values in multiple transects. The trend analysis shows that some areas are experiencing notable shoreline retreat (negative trends), while others display mild accretion (positive trends). However, in several transects, the high standard deviation suggests that short-term variability in shoreline position is larger than the long-term trend (Figure 2).
- Santa Susanna Beach: Santa Susanna shows moderate variability in its coastline. Some transects indicate significant retreat (red areas) alternating with stretches of relative stability or slight growth (green and blue areas). The standard deviation confirms this irregularity, being more marked towards the center of the studied stretch, where erosion seems to be more intensely concentrated (Figure 3).
- Altafulla Beach: Altafulla exhibits relatively stable patterns along the coastline, with low variability and limited standard deviation in most transects. However, some specific areas show significant localized setbacks (dark red areas), although the general trend indicates stability (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Trends and Standard Deviation of Coastline Change at Pals Beach

Figure 3. Trends and Standard Deviation of Coastline Change at Santa Susana Beach

Figure 4. Trends and Standard Deviation of Coastline Change at Altafulla Beach.

6 Conclusion

The methodological approach demonstrated high accuracy in detecting and analyzing shoreline changes. Key findings include:

High accuracy in shoreline detection

The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) method outperformed other classification methods (K-means and Slope Index) in most cases, providing the most reliable land-water classification.

NDWI achieved lower RMSE values (11.2–21.37m), ensuring sub-pixel accuracy.

Comparison with other methods

NDWI showed higher accuracy than K-means and Slope Index due to its ability to better distinguish land and water boundaries.

K-means had greater variability in shoreline positions, while Slope Index results were inconsistent across different beach environments.

Significant shoreline variability in some beaches

Pals Beach: Showed high fluctuations in shoreline position, indicating dynamic sediment transport and erosion patterns.

Santa Susanna Beach: Displayed notable peaks in shoreline position, likely influenced by human activities and infrastructure interaction.

Need for continuous monitoring

The high variability observed in Pals and Santa Susanna beaches suggests active coastal dynamics, emphasizing the need for regular monitoring and adaptive coastal management.

Localized differences in erosion dynamics

7 Acknowledgements

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The work presented here has been developed during the IMPETUS project. IMPETUS focused on increasing our resilience. Working with local citizens, policy-makers and businesses in our demonstration sites around Europe, our teams are analysing solutions, boosting knowledge, and creating packages of adaptation measures that other communities can use as a pathway towards a climate-neutral and sustainable future. It was launched in October 2021 to turn climate commitments into tangible, urgent actions to protect communities and the planet.

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